

Evaluating the Impact of Ash on Heavy Metals and Total Hydrocarbons Remediation in Crude Oil Contaminated Soils

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Received: February 16, 2025; Accepted: April 1, 2025; Published: April 29, 2025

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15302457>

Abstract: This research aimed at evaluating the impact of ash on heavy metals and hydrocarbons remediation in crude oil-contaminated soils. The study was conducted in Soil Science Laboratory Imo State University, Owerri. The collected soil was air-dried, sieved, and analyzed before the incubation experiment. Palm bunch, palm mesocarp, and wood were used for ash preparation. The ashes were prepared by controlled combustion. Soil samples were contaminated with crude oil at 10% contamination rate and allowed to stand for two weeks. The soils were amended with ash at varying application rates of 5t/ha, 10t/ha and 20t/ha respectively. The mixed soils were incubated for 4, 8, and 12 weeks respectively. Prior to incubation the used soil and ash was analyzed to determine the status and the chemical composition of the used soil and ash respectively. Soil pH, soil organic carbon, heavy metals content, and total hydrocarbons content were analyzed at the end of each week intervals. The chemical analysis of the ashes revealed that palm bunch ash and palm mesocarp ash had elevated pH values (10.9 and 10.3), while wood ash was neutral (7.3). Palm bunch ash also had the highest levels of carbon and nitrogen. The levels of elemental contents of all the ashes were of high values. Ash application increased soil pH, with the highest value found in soils amended with palm bunch ash (PBA) @ 20t/ha which was maintained across the incubation intervals. Organic carbon content showed variation among the treatments and across the incubation intervals with wood ash (WA) @ 20t/ha showing the highest value. The use of ash significantly reduced heavy metal concentrations, but higher heavy metal content were observed at higher ash level application. WA @ 5t/ha was most effective in reducing cadmium. Application of ash also promoted the degradation of hydrocarbons, although at higher ash levels the rate of hydrocarbon breakdown was reduced. In all the use of coarse textured ash (WA) at lower level (5t/ha) is good for the remediation of heavy metals especially Cd while the use of fine textured ash like (PBA) at lower level (5 – 10t/ha) is good for the remediation of total hydrocarbons in crude oil contaminated soil but caution should be applied on the level of application, since excess application can reduce the remediation efficiency.

Keywords: Ash, Heavy metals, Total hydrocarbons, Remediation, Crude oil-contaminated soil

Introduction

Soil contamination by crude oil is a major environmental problem, particularly in oil-

producing regions where spills, pipeline leaks, and exploration activities lead to severe land degradation. Crude oil pollution

negatively impacts soil physicochemical properties, reducing fertility, altering microbial communities, and leading to the accumulation of toxic substances such as heavy metals and hydrocarbons (Song et al., 2019). These pollutants pose significant environmental and human health risks due to their persistence, toxicity, and potential bioaccumulation (Zhang et al., 2021).

Traditional remediation strategies such as soil washing, chemical oxidation, and bioremediation have been employed to mitigate crude oil contamination (Huang et al., 2020). However, these methods often require significant financial investment, may lead to secondary pollution, and can be ineffective for complete remediation, particularly in heavy metal-laden soils. In recent years, researchers have explored the use of natural amendments, including biochar and ash, to enhance the remediation of contaminated soils (Beesley et al., 2011). Ash, derived from biomass combustion is rich in alkaline compounds, minerals, and porous structures, which make it an effective amendment for improving soil conditions and promoting the degradation of organic pollutants (Oleszczuk et al., 2012).

Crude oil spills introduce complex mixtures of hydrocarbons and heavy metals into the soil, leading to long-term contamination that reduces agricultural productivity and threatens ecosystems (Okonwu and Onuh, 2021). Heavy metals such as lead (Pb),

cadmium (Cd), and arsenic (As) often co-exist with petroleum hydrocarbons, exacerbating soil toxicity and making remediation challenging (Kuppusamy et al., 2017). Conventional soil remediation approaches, such as excavation and chemical treatment, have limitations, including high costs and potential secondary pollution.

Ash, as a byproduct of biomass combustion, has shown promise in soil remediation due to its ability to neutralize acidic soils, adsorb contaminants, and enhance microbial activity (Wang et al., 2023). However, there is limited research on its effectiveness in crude oil-contaminated soils, particularly concerning its impact on heavy metals and hydrocarbon degradation. Understanding the mechanisms by which ash influences the immobilization and bioavailability of heavy metals, as well as the breakdown of petroleum hydrocarbons, is critical for developing cost-effective and sustainable soil remediation strategies.

The application of ash in soil remediation offers a sustainable and environmentally friendly approach to mitigating crude oil contamination. Ash contains alkaline minerals that can neutralize soil acidity and improve microbial conditions necessary for hydrocarbon degradation (Ahmad et al., 2016). Additionally, the high adsorption capacity of ash can reduce the mobility and bioavailability of heavy metals, potentially

lowering toxicity levels in contaminated soils (Shaheen et al., 2019).

This study is significant as it provides insight into the potential of ash as a low-cost amendment for the remediation of crude oil-contaminated soils. The findings will contribute to existing knowledge on soil restoration, aid policymakers in developing remediation guidelines, and support sustainable waste management by utilizing ash from biomass combustion. However, given the growing environmental concerns surrounding petroleum pollution in oil producing areas, this study will focus on evaluating the impact of ash on heavy metals and total hydrocarbons remediation in crude oil contaminated soils.

Materials and Method

Site Description

The incubation experiment was conducted at the Soil Science Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, Imo State University, Owerri. Owerri is located in Nigeria's southeastern rain forest zone, between latitude 05°6' and longitude 06°07'E. The area experiences a bimodal rainfall pattern, with wet seasons from April to July and September to November, and a short dry period in August, often referred to as the 'August break.' The region has a mean annual maximum rainfall of 2238mm, with temperatures ranging from 23°C to 32°C, and a relative humidity

ranging from 63% to 80%. The dominant soil type in this area is Ultisols.

Sample collection and preparation

Soil samples with no history of pollution were collected from the Research Farm of Imo State University, Owerri, at a depth of 0 - 15 cm using a shovel. The samples were mixed into a composite following the procedure outlined by the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO, 2007). The composite samples were air-dried, crushed, and sieved using a 2mm sieve. Crude oil for the study was sourced from the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) in Warri, Nigeria. Palm bunches and mesocarp of oil palm was collected from an oil mill in Ngor Okpala, while sawdust was purchased from a timber market. The ashes used in the treatments were prepared by controlled combustion and characterized.

Incubation Experiment

500g of the air-dried and sieved soil sample was weighed using a balance and placed into appropriately labeled plastic plates with covers. 50ml of crude oil, corresponding to a 10% contamination level, was measured with a measuring cylinder and added to each plate. The purpose of this pollution was to simulate a severe contamination scenario, as crude oil concentrations above 3% are known to be increasingly harmful to soil (Osuji et al., 2005; Akpoveta et al., 2011).

The soil and oil mixture were thoroughly blended, and the setup was left for two weeks under natural conditions to allow for the acclimatization of the soil to the oil (Onyelucheya et al., 2013). Immediately after 2 weeks contaminated soils in the plates was amended with the ash derived from palm bunch, palm mesocarp and wood at the rate of 5t/ha, 10t/ha and 20t/ha (1.5g, 2.5g and 5g) respectively. The soils were mixed thoroughly with their respective treatments and water was added at field capacity. Contaminated soils without any amendment were the control. The soils were allowed to stay for two weeks without covering while maintaining the experimental pot at field capacity after which the incubation commences. The incubated pot was allowed to stay for 4, 8 and 12 weeks during the period of incubation. The experimental design used was factorial in complete randomized design with ash treatments as factor A and incubation weeks as factor B. Sampling of the soil was done after each incubation weeks to determine pH, OC, Cr, Cd, Ni and Total petroleum hydrocarbons. Destructive sampling was used in this experiment.

Laboratory Analysis

Soil pH was measured using the Electrometric method (Ahmedna et al. 1997). Organic carbon content was determined by the wet combustion method,

specifically the Nelson and Sommers Method (1982). The concentrations of Chromium, Cadmium, and Nickel were assessed using an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) following the procedures outlined by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (Williams, 2000). The total petroleum hydrocarbon content was measured with a Spectronics 20 spectrophotometer at 420nm after extracting with 10ml of toluene.

Statistical Analysis

The results from the laboratory analyses were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DUMRT) was used to separate the treatment means at a 5% significance level. The interrelationship between selected soil properties and the heavy metals and total hydrocarbons were done using correlation analysis.

Results and Discussion

The initial Soil characteristics prior to the incubation experiment

Before incubation, the soil texture of the unpolluted sample was found to be loamy sand, with 85% sand, 3% silt, and 12% clay (Table 1). This soil type typically originates from coarse parent material. (Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources (1990) and highly prone to leaching. The pH of the soil is 4.6, the

nutrients level of soil revealed 14.7mg kg⁻¹ phosphorus, 1.26g kg⁻¹ nitrogen, 16.19g kg⁻¹ organic matter, 0.05cmolc kg⁻¹ sodium, 0.37cmolc kg⁻¹ potassium, 0.95cmolc kg⁻¹ magnesium, 1.76cmolc kg⁻¹ calcium, 0.70cmolc kg⁻¹ aluminum, 0.10cmolc kg⁻¹ hydrogen and CEC of 8.0cmolc kg⁻¹. According to Esu (1991), nitrogen, soil

organic matter, calcium and potassium were of low range while phosphorus, magnesium and cation exchange capacity were of medium range. The soil physicochemical properties of the used soil are inherently low in soil fertility, which is peculiar to soils found on the tropics (Sanchez, 1976).

Table 1 Selected physicochemical properties of initial soil before the incubation study

Soil parameters	Values
Sand (%)	85.0
Silt (%)	3.0
Clay (%)	12.0
Textural class	Loamy sand
Soil pH	4.6
Available Phosphorus (mgkg ⁻¹)	14.7
Total nitrogen (gkg ⁻¹)	1.26
Organic matter(gkg ⁻¹)	16.19
Exchangeable cations	
Calcium (cmolckg ⁻¹)	1.76
Magnesium (cmolckg ⁻¹)	0.95
Potassium (cmolckg ⁻¹)	0.37
Sodium (cmolckg ⁻¹)	0.05
Cation exchange capacity (cmolckg ⁻¹)	8.0
Exchangeable acidity	
Hydrogen ion (cmolkg ⁻¹)	0.10
Aluminium ion (cmolkg ⁻¹)	0.70

Chemical composition of the ashes used for the incubation study

The chemical composition of the three produced ashes used in this study is depicted in Table 2. The pH of the ashes revealed near neutral to alkaline with values of 10.9, 10.3 and 7.3 in palm bunch, palm mesocarp

and wood respectively. The pH of the ashes could aid the remediation of polluted soil. This is because it provides the buffering effect in the soil during mineralization of crude oil (Akan et al., 2013). The three produced ashes generally had high carbon content and moderate amount of nitrogen. The elemental contents of the ashes

constitute 2201.08, 2723.37 and 298.45 mg kg⁻¹ of phosphorus, 110.5, 280.5 and 416.5 mg kg⁻¹ of calcium, 1683.0, 1513.0 and 1946.5 mg kg⁻¹ of magnesium, 801.03, 840.11 and 820.57 mg kg⁻¹ of potassium and 101.92, 203.31 and 152.92 mg kg⁻¹ of sodium in palm bunch ash (PBA), palm mesocarp ash (PMA) and wood ash (WA) respectively. The level of elemental contents

of the ashes is suspected to aid the growth of bacteria already in the used soil. This is because of the essentiality of nutrient for microbes degrading contaminants. This assertion is supported by the works of Gallego et al., (2001), who demonstrated the important factors that enhance soil bioremediation.

Table 2 The chemical composition of the ashes used for the incubation study

Ash	pH (H ₂ O)	Total C	Total N	Total P	Total Ca	Total Mg	Total K	Total Na
		g kg ⁻¹						
Palm Bunch	10.9	34.31	2.10	2201.08	110.5	1683.0	801.03	101.92
Palm Mesocarp	10.3	31.92	1.82	2723.37	280.5	1513.0	840.11	203.31
Wood	7.3	33.12	1.54	298.45	416.5	1946.5	820.57	152.92

The impact of ash treatment on Soil pH

The result of pH (Table 4) shows increases with ashes application, which increases with increase on the amount of ash applied. PBA @ 20t/ha gave the highest pH value (10.80) which was maintained across the incubation intervals from 4 weeks to 12 weeks. The lowest pH was on unamended soil at 8 weeks incubation interval (6.4). The observed increase in pH is an indication that ash reduces the acidity of the crude oil contaminated soil. The increase in soil pH is

attributed to the higher pH (alkalinity) of ash resulting to base saturation, increase in surface charge enabling ash to attract polar organic molecules and ionized organic contaminants (Guo et al., 2020). The result is in conformity with the findings of Zhang et al. (2016). According to Sani et al., (2023) addition of coconut shell activated carbon (CSAC) on crude oil contaminated soil significant increase the pH of the remediated soil.

Table 3 Results of the repeated measures (ANOVA) analysis conducted with General Liner Model (GLM) indicating the P values and significant level of the treatment, week, and treatment with week interactions of parameters

Factors	Ash Treatment		Weeks		Ash Treatment*Weeks	
	P values	Significant Level	P values	Significant Level	P values	Significant Level
pH	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***
OC	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***
Cr	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***
Cd	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***
Ni	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***
THCs	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***	<0.0001	***

Notes: ns (not significant); and *, **, and ***, denote significant differences at $P < 0.05$, $P < 0.01$, and $P < 0.001$, respectively. OC = Organic carbon, Cr = Chromium, Cd = Cadmium, Ni = Nickel, THCs = Total hydrocarbons

Table 4 Effect of ash treatments on soil pH at different intervals of incubation

Treatments	Soil pH		
	Week 4	Week 8	Week 12
PBA @ 5t/ha	10.00 ± 0.00 ^c	10.20 ± 0.00 ^c	10.10 ± 0.00 ^c
PMA @ 5t/ha	8.23 ± 0.06 ^f	8.40 ± 0.00 ^e	8.50 ± 0.00 ^f
WA @ 5t/ha	6.70 ± 0.00 ^h	6.80 ± 0.00 ^g	7.00 ± 0.00 ^h
PBA @ 10t/ha	10.60 ± 0.00 ^b	10.60 ± 0.00 ^b	10.60 ± 0.00 ^b
PMA @ 10t/ha	8.60 ± 0.00 ^e	8.40 ± 0.00 ^e	8.60 ± 0.00 ^e
WA @ 10t/ha	6.70 ± 0.00 ^h	6.80 ± 0.00 ^g	7.00 ± 0.00 ^h
PBA @ 20t/ha	10.80 ± 0.00 ^a	10.80 ± 0.00 ^a	10.80 ± 0.00 ^a
PMA @ 20t/ha	9.00 ± 0.00 ^d	8.67 ± 0.06 ^d	9.00 ± 0.00 ^d
WA @ 20t/ha	6.90 ± 0.00 ^g	6.90 ± 0.00 ^f	7.20 ± 0.00 ^g
Control	6.70 ± 0.10 ^h	6.40 ± 0.10 ^h	6.50 ± 0.10 ⁱ

Note: Means within the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$ (DNMRT). The column represents the mean values ± standard deviation of triplicates. PBA = Palm bunch ash, PMA = Palm mesocarp ash, WA = Wood ash

The impact of ash treatment on soil organic carbon

Organic carbon content of soils that received crude oil treatment with no ash amendment showed high value of soil organic carbon though not the highest. The high organic carbon content observed in the control corroborated with the works of Wang et al., (2010) who reported that oil

contamination significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) increase the organic carbon contents of soils. This is probably because of the much higher total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs) concentration (Wang et al., 2013). Similar findings have been reported by Agbogidi and Ejemeta (2005) who concluded that high organic carbon in crude oil-contaminated soil might be due to the slow

decomposition rate by soil organisms since contamination of soil with crude oil might have poor soil aeration. The results of the SOC showed significant variations among the ash amended soil (Table 5). The soil with the highest SOC was that treated with wood ash @ 20t/ha (3.431%) at both 4 and 8 weeks incubation intervals. The lowest

SOC value was seen on soil amended with PMA @ 5t/ha (2.793%) at 12 week incubation interval. Despite been significant the variations among the treated pots were not wide apart. This is because the carbon content of the used ashes varied slightly with each other (Table 2).

Table 5: Effect of ash treatments on soil organic carbon at different intervals of incubation

Treatments	Organic Carbon (%)		
	Week 4	Week 8	Week 12
PBA @ 5t/ha	2.834±0.001 ^h	2.951±0.002 ^{fg}	2.918±0.005 ^f
PMA @ 5t/ha	2.895±0.031 ^g	2.895±0.031 ^g	2.793±0.000 ^g
WA @ 5t/ha	3.077±0.009 ^e	3.193±0.005 ^{cd}	2.931±0.023 ^f
PBA @ 10t/ha	3.116±0.004 ^d	3.154±0.003 ^d	2.951±0.002 ^f
PMA @ 10t/ha	3.112±0.000 ^d	2.994±0.002 ^{ef}	2.994±0.002 ^e
WA @ 10t/ha	3.357±0.007 ^b	3.248±0.111 ^{bc}	3.232±0.000 ^c
PBA @ 20t/ha	3.116±0.004 ^d	3.274±0.002 ^b	3.194±0.002 ^d
PMA @ 20t/ha	3.238±0.007 ^c	3.035±0.003 ^e	3.306±0.063 ^b
WA @ 20t/ha	3.431±0.000 ^a	3.431±0.000 ^a	3.357±0.007 ^a
Control	3.035±0.003 ^f	3.154±0.000 ^d	3.238±0.006 ^c

Note: Means within the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$ (DNMRT). The column represents the mean values \pm standard deviation of triplicates. PBA = Palm bunch ash, PMA = Palm mesocarp ash, WA = Wood ash

The impact of ash treatment on selected heavy metals (Cr, Cd and Ni)

The results of the impact of ash on heavy metals of crude oil contaminated soil within 12 weeks incubation intervals using ash produced from different agricultural waste are shown in figure 1. The results obtained show that the different types of ash used in the incubation experiment significantly reduce heavy metal concentration in crude oil contaminated soil. Despite that higher concentration of heavy metals were seen at

higher levels of ash application, wood ash @ 5t/ha reduces Cd more at the different levels but have low effect on Cr and Ni when compared with other ashes used. The variations obtained is because the different types of ash used have varying chemical composition, physical properties and mechanisms of action, liable to affect their performance in immobilizing heavy metals (Nabeela et al., 2015; Ahmaruzzaman 2010; Khan et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2010, Okoro et al., 2019).

Among the three ashes used in this study, as the level of applied ash increases the rate of remediation decreases. This might be attributed to the reduction in the remediation efficiency with increase quantity of applied ash. Ash is alkaline in nature and in the study the applied ash are 10.9, 10.3 and 7.3 in PBA, PMA and WA respectively (Table 2). The ashes when applied in excessive quantity may raise the soil pH so high which could induce alkalinity stress and suppress

microbial activity, thus reducing biodegradation rates of crude oil contaminants (Mahmood et al., 2003). Bang-Andreasen et al., (2017) found that excessive wood ash application led to pH values above 9.0 which inhibit microbial population and reducing hydrocarbon degradation. Ubuoh et al., (2018a) also observed reduced microbial activity when large amount of palm bunch ash were applied leading to slower remediation rates.

Figure 1 The impact of ash on Chromium, Cadmium and Nickel concentration at different intervals of incubation

Total Hydrocarbons (THCs)

Based on the results obtained on total hydrocarbons, addition of ashes to crude oil contaminated soil stimulated biodegradation of total hydrocarbons but rate of remediation was reduced with increased level of ash application. This is evidenced by the higher percentage availability of Total hydrocarbons as the level of ash application increases (Figure 2). The different types of ash responded different in biodegradation of THCs with increase in ash level. This is because the different ashes have varying physical and chemical properties that can impact on soil porosity, aggregation, water retention, all of which are critical for effective bioremediation of crude oil contaminated soils. PMA showed less biodegradation of THCs followed by WA. The result of PMA is because fine textured ashes like PMA can fill soil pores,

thus reducing aeration and permeability. The reduction of aeration limits oxygen availability for aerobic microbial degradation of hydrocarbons (Jala and Goyal, 2006). Coarse ash like wood ash and rice husk ash may improve soil structure initially but can lead to compact if over applied (Khan et al., 2016). PBA presents higher effect on biodegradation of THCs when compared with the unamended soils. Application of PMA@ 20t/h had slightly higher THCs than unamended soils. The trend observed with PBA might be attributed to the fact that ashes with high organic content such as palm bunch ash are less cohesive and may improve soil aggregation temporarily. This result on PBA was in line with Obuoh et al., (2018b) of which initial improvement was observed but later showed decline as seen in 20t/ha.

Figure 2 The impact of ash on Total hydrocarbons at different intervals of incubation
Correlation between the soil properties (soil pH and soil organic carbon), selected heavy metals and total hydrocarbon in the three produced ashes

The interrelationship between soil pH, soil organic carbon and selected heavy metals in respect with the type of ash are presented in Table 6. Ashes can alter soil pH and chemical properties which impact heavily on heavy metal behavior. The relationship between pH and heavy metals of PBA used showed that there is significant positive correlation between soil pH and all the selected heavy metals evaluated in this study (Table 6). They are Cr (0.67), Cd (0.81) and Ni (0.77). PMA also follow the same trend as seen with PBA with soil pH except that relation with Cr which though positive but was not significant. The relationship implies that increase in soil pH increases the mobility of the selected heavy metals. WA showed none (Cd 0.0) to very poor positive correlation (Cr (0.08) and Ni (0.39)).

The variation found in WA comparative to PBA and PMA might be attributed to the present of carbonate in WA. According to Ubuoh et al., (2018b), ashes with high carbonate content can stabilize pH, mitigate fluctuations that might otherwise increase heavy metal mobility or form precipitate with carbonate making it unavailable. Significant relationship found between soil pH and Cr on soils treated with PBA could be linked with its chemical composition (Table 2). PBA had the highest pH compare to other ashes used for the study and likely excessive soil pH could be attained with increase in quantity applied. Excessive pH in the soil increases desorption of some heavy metal of which Cr is among. Cr primarily exists as Cr^{3+} under acidic condition but under alkaline condition it changes to Cr^{6+} which is an anionic species and is weakly adsorbed leading to more Cr

in the soil (Barnhart, 1997; James and Bartlett, 1983; Shanker et al., 2005). Cd at increased pH form precipitate which makes it's to be insoluble (Alloway, 1995). It (Cr) can as well form complexes which could further reduce its solubility but may also mobilize if soluble complexes are formed (Sauvé et al., 2000). In this study, the complexes formed are soluble as it could be seen that with the relationship between soil organic carbon and selected heavy metals. SOC showed a positive and significant correlation with the studied heavy metals across the three ashes used (Table 6). Hydrocarbons are generally nonpolar and hydrophobic, meaning they have low water solubility. Soil pH has minimal direct impact on the solubility of most hydrocarbons but can influence their partitioning in the soil matrix in relation to adsorption and mobility. Soil pH on the other hand has a more pronounced effect on

the biological degradation of hydrocarbons. In this study, the significant positive correlation results with pH and THCs in all the evaluated ashes and the negative significant correlation on WA, make clear evidence that the variations observed is a function of the texture of the ash used. Fine textured ash of which PMA and PBA could be ascribed to have the potential to fill the soil pores. Thus, reducing aeration in the soil and indirectly reduced the activities of the microbes with the responsibility of degrading hydrocarbons. Hence, more of it is available even as soil pH increases (Jala and Goyal, 2006). Also according to Khan et al., (2016), coarse textured ashes improve soil structure initially but over application could compact the soil. On the average with WA there is reduction of THCs with pH and increase with SOC which is of weak positive but significant (0.58).

Table 6 Correlation between the soil properties (soil pH and soil organic carbon), heavy metals and total hydrocarbon in incubation study in relation to the types of ash

Soil properties	Cr (mg/kg)	Cd (mg/kg)	Ni (mg/kg)	THCs (%)
PBA				
Soil pH	0.67**	0.81**	0.77**	0.77**
Soil organic carbon	0.48	0.73**	0.61**	0.79**
PMA				
Soil pH	0.42	0.56*	0.86**	0.53*
Soil organic carbon	0.54*	0.64**	0.80**	0.63**
WA				
Soil pH	0.08	0.00	0.39	-0.62**
Soil organic carbon	0.86**	0.65**	0.79**	0.58*

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Conclusion

The effectiveness of ash to remediate heavy metals and total hydrocarbons depends on the chemical composition, physical properties and mechanism actions. Mechanism actions in this research are strongly controlled by the type and quantity of ash. Types of ash play a critical role in remediating crude oil contaminated soil in incubation experiments. The different ashes used increased pH and nutrient supply which could enhance microbial activities and hydrocarbon breakdown. But varying physical properties arising from the different type of ash used could have impacted strongly on soil porosity, aggregate, water retention and aeration, all of which are critical for effective bioremediation of crude oil contaminated soils. Excessive quantity of ash raises the soil pH so high which induce alkalinity stress and suppress microbial activity, thus reducing biodegradation rates of crude oil contaminants. Again, the type of ashes used in this remediation significantly affects the remediation efficiency. However, the use of coarse textured ash (WA) at lower level (5t/ha) is good for the remediation of heavy metals especially Cd while the use of fine textured ash like (PBA) at lower level (5 – 10t/ha) is good for the remediation of total hydrocarbons in crude oil contaminated soil but caution should be applied on the level of application, since excess application can reduce the remediation efficiency. Large

scale of this experiment in the pot experiment and subsequently in the field is recommended to evaluate how uptake by plant could be affected with ash application in relation to types and levels of ashes applied.

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